

ionisation. However, the non-electrolytic nature of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_4(\text{Pybmz})_2]$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$ and both the varieties of $[\text{MoOBr}_3\text{Pybmz}]$ was established from molar conductance data (Table 1) in dimethylsulphoxide⁹. The μ_{eff} values are in fair agreement with d^1 configuration of molybdenum(v). The hydrolytic product $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$ is diamagnetic due to oxo-bridging¹⁰ with the possible Mo-Mo interaction. The terminal $\nu_{\text{Mo}=\text{O}}$ band¹⁰ at 975 cm^{-1} in $\text{PybmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ shifted to 955 cm^{-1} in the hydrolytic product $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2(\text{Pybmz})_2]$. Such lowering of $\nu_{\text{Mo}=\text{O}}$ can be attributed to the replacement of bromide by oxygen¹¹. Electronic spectra of the salt $\text{PybmzH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_3]$ in 9 M HBr show two bands at $14\ 500$ and $22\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{I})$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, and four charge transfer bands at $24\ 200$, $25\ 800$, $30\ 000$ and $41\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{II})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{II})$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{III})$, respectively. For the remaining complexes the electronic spectral bands appeared around $13\ 800$, $22\ 000$, $25\ 000$, $31\ 000$ and $42\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, $L \rightarrow \text{Mo}$ charge transfer, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{I})$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(\text{II})$ transitions, respectively.

References

1. H. K. SAHA, S. S. MANDAL and T. K. ROYCHAUDHURI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 840.
2. H. K. SAHA, M. BAGCHI and S. CHAKRABARTI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 455.
3. H. K. SAHA, B. K. SIKDAR and T. K. ROYCHAUDHURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 723.
4. H. K. SAHA, S. S. MANDAL and P. C. GHORAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1124; H. K. SAHA, A. SAHA and S. S. MANDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 902.
5. T. R. HARKINS, J. L. WALTER, O. E. HARRIS and H. FREISER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 260; T. J. LANE, J. NAKAGAWOY, J. L. WALTER and A. J. CANDATHIL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 267.
6. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1911.
7. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd. ed., Longman, London, p. 493.
8. W. G. PALMER, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1959.
9. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **7**, 110.
10. M. C. BAIRD, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **9**, 29.
11. J. SELBIN, L. H. HOLMES and S. P. MEGHLYN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1359.

Complexes of 2,4-Dimercapto-*s*-triazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole with some Platinum Metal Ions. Part-II

P. D. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 10 February 1988, accepted 25 March 1988

IN an early communication¹, the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with 2,4-dimercapto-*s*-triazolo[4,3-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (abbreviated as DTTH_2) have been reported. Now we report the complexes of Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} , Ru^{II} and Rh^{III} with DTTH_2 . Previously it was shown¹ that DTTH_2 coordinates

either as a monobasic or a dibasic acidic molecule in basic medium. Now we have found that DTTH_2 can coordinate as a neutral sulphur donor as well with platinum metal ions (Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) in acidic solution ($\text{pH} \approx 1-2$).

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the reported method². The metal salts used were of Johnson Mathey.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$M(\text{DTTH}_2)_2\text{Cl}_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ or Pt^{II}) : An ethanolic solution ($\text{pH} \approx 1-2$) of the metal chloride (0.001 mol in 20 ml) and hot ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.002 mol in 30 ml) were mixed with stirring when dichloro complexes separated immediately. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in an air-oven at $50-60^\circ$.

$M(\text{DTTH})_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$, Pt^{II} or Ru^{II}) and $\text{Rh}(\text{DTTH})_2 \cdot 1.5\text{ H}_2\text{O}$: Ethanolic solutions of the metal (Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} or Ru^{II}) chloride or rhodium(III) chloride (0.001 mol in 30 ml) and the ligand in stoichiometric ratio were mixed and refluxed on a steam-bath for $\sim 1\text{ h}$, when the complex separated gradually. It was filtered, washed and dried as above.

$\text{Ru}(\text{DTT})\text{Py} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous ethanolic solution of ruthenium(II) chloride (0.002 mol in 30 ml) and the ligand (0.002 mol in 30 ml) were mixed and refluxed with pyridine (5 ml) on a steam-bath for 0.5 h when a dark green precipitate separated out gradually. The product was filtered, washed and dried as above.

$M(\text{DTT})\text{Py}_2$ ($M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ or Pt^{II}) and $\text{Rh}_2(\text{DTT})_2 \cdot \text{Py}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (0.002 mol in 30 ml) was made alkaline by adding excess pyridine and refluxed with the ligand dissolved in ethanol-pyridine mixture in stoichiometric proportion ($\text{pH} = 7-8$) when red or yellow complex separated out immediately. The precipitate was digested on a steam-bath, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over KOH in an atmosphere of pyridine.

The colour and analytical results of the complexes are shown in Table 1. Ir spectra of the complexes were recorded³ in the range $4\ 000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The solid reflectance spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU 500 spectrophotometer in the range $220-850\text{ nm}$ taking MgCO_3 as the standard.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are almost insoluble in water as well as in the usual organic solvents; however, the complexes $M(\text{DTTH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $M(\text{DTTH})_2$ are slightly soluble in DMF. The hydrated complexes retain water molecules below $90-100^\circ$ indicating that they are strongly held up in crystal lattices or bonded to the metal atom. The pyridine adducts are also stable in air and do not lose pyridine below

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		M	N	OI
Pd(DTTH) ₂	Orange red	21.83 (21.96)	23.27 (23.12)	—
Pt(DTTH) ₂	Yellowish	34.42 (34.04)	19.32 (19.54)	—
Ru(DTTH) ₂	Black	21.73 (21.51)	23.10 (23.37)	—
Rh(DTTH) ₂ .1.5H ₂ O	Red	14.81	24.07	—
Pd(DTTH) ₂ .Cl ₂	Reddish brown	19.27 (19.08)	19.98 (20.09)	12.56 (12.73)
Pt(DTTH) ₂ .Cl ₂	Yellowish brown	30.70 (30.19)	17.13 (17.33)	10.95 (10.98)
Pd(DTT)Py ₂	Red	23.62 (23.51)	18.47 (18.56)	—
Pt(DTT)Py ₂	Yellow	36.41 (36.05)	15.25 (15.52)	—
Ru(DTT)Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark green	25.01 (25.01)	17.12 (17.32)	—
Rh ₂ (DTT) ₂ .Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dull red	21.52 (21.35)	20.12 (20.33)	—

* Py=Pyridine.

110° indicating that pyridine is also bonded to the metal atom. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic which confirms the presence of oxidation state of +3 for Rh and +2 for Ru, Pd and Pt. The diamagnetism of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes suggests their four-coordinated square-planar structure. The diamagnetism of Ru^{II} and Rh^{III} complexes suggest their octahedral geometry.

The complex Pd(DTTH)₂ exhibits a medium band at 17 860 cm⁻¹ assignable to ¹A_{1g}→³A_{2g} transition in square planar field⁴. The rhodium complex Rh(DTTH)₂.1.5H₂O displays a strong band near 22 200 cm⁻¹ due to charge transfer and, a shoulder near 19 230 cm⁻¹ due to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} transition in distorted octahedral field^{5,6}. A broad and weak band at 16 930 cm⁻¹ in the reflectance spectra of Ru(DTT)Py₂.2H₂O can be assigned to ¹A_{1g}→¹T_{2g} transition in approximately octahedral field. Other complexes do not display distinct band in the visible region. The Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes M(DTTH)₂ and M(DTTH)₂.Cl₂ do not display distinct band but display a broad absorption below near 23 500 cm⁻¹ attributable to charge transfer absorption as the band is located at lower energy than the expected ligand field transition^{4,7}.

The ligand displays SH stretch at 2 460 cm⁻¹ which disappears in almost all the complexes indicating the coordination of the ligand through deprotonated (SH) sulphur. The broad NH stretch of the ligand (2 900–3 090 cm⁻¹) disappears in the complexes containing the dianionic ligand but retains as distinct band at 3 200–3 300 cm⁻¹ in the complexes containing monoanionic as well neutral ligand indicating that one of the thioamide NH is not involved in bonding in the complexes with monoanion or neutral ligand while involved in coordination in complexes with dianionic ligand. The hydrated complexes display a broad band at 3 400 cm⁻¹ attributed from ν_{OH} of water molecule.

The δ_{NH} (1 491 cm⁻¹) and τ_{NH} (787 cm⁻¹) bands also disappear in the complexes with dianionic ligand, while these are raised to higher frequency in the complexes with neutral and monoanionic ligand and observed at 1 522±8 and 792±10 cm⁻¹, respectively. In finger print and far-infrared region, the ligand displays a number of bands due to thioamide groups, ring skeletal vibrations and ring deformation vibrations⁸; but in the complexes with dianionic ligand most of them disappear and are observed as broad and medium bands indicating that both the thioamide groups are involved in coordination and the complexes M(DTT)Py₂ (M=Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}), Ru(DTT)Py₂.2H₂O and Rh₂(DTT)₂.Py₂.2H₂O are polymeric. The thioamide bands I (1 491 and 1 470 cm⁻¹) of the ligand are raised to higher frequency and merge together with ν_{C=N} of the ligand and observed as a broad band at 1 505–1 530 cm⁻¹. The thioamide band⁹ IV (917 cm⁻¹) shifted to lower frequency and appeared at 805±15 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of the thioamide group. The pyridine adduct complexes display a medium band at 1 610 (CN) and 1 010± cm⁻¹ (pyridine ring breathing mode) suggesting the coordination of pyridine nitrogen in complexes¹⁰.

References

1. P. D. SINGH, N. K. JHA and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 282.
2. J. SANDSTROM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, 15, 1295.
3. S. J. LAPLACA and J. A. IBERS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 778.
4. W. ROY MASON and H. B. GRAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 5221.
5. J. SCHERZER, P. PHILLIPS, L. OLAPP and J. EDWARDS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 847.
6. H. H. SCHMIDTKE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1965, 339, 103; B. T. HEATON and H. SHAW, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 589.
7. H. B. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 85, 260.
8. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1967.
9. N. F. CURTIS and Y. M. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 804.
10. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTALL, D. E. SCAIFF and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 18, 79.

Synthesis and Characterisation of Mercury(II) Complexes of some Aromatic Amine N-Oxides

R. K. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Lajpat Rai (Post-Graduate) College, Sahibabad-201 005

Manuscript received 23 October 1986, revised 18 March 1988, accepted 6 April 1988

THIS paper reports the synthesis and characterisation of Hg^{II} complexes with 5,6-benzoquinoline-N-oxide (Benzqno) (I) and 2-ethoxycarbonyl-